

A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW OF GEN Z'S LEARNING CHARACTERISTICS AND PREFERENCES

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INTRODUCTION:

Economic, political and other major events experienced by the generational cohorts creates a unique value system resulting to characteristics distinct to generational mind sets and group tendencies. (Rothman). These distinct characteristics are oftentimes studied because it will served as bases of every institution on what strategies are to be employed to specifically determine the needs of each generational members and how to maximize each characteristics to find potentials within. And the current and the biggest generation today: the generation z, the digital natives, or the post-millennial is not an exemption to this.

Generation Z kids born after 1995, is on the microscope today. The first truly digital natives, they are the ones who have breathed and lived the world of smartphones, social media, internet, multi-tasking, gaming, and the virtual world. However, they were also made to face the world of terrorism, economic decline and recession, under-employment, scandals and plagues. This extreme life experiences allows them to be connected on a borderless world where uncertainty became one tool to survive.

This uncertainty became a challenge for most educators in delivering maximum transfer of learning for the generation z because questioning of the relevance and utilities of concepts and principles to the outside world are being raised. A tremendous shift from traditional classroom to 21st century classroom must then be rewired to ensure that lifelong learning will be made significant to the uncertain world.

Rewiring classrooms usually starts with studying the value systems, behaviour, attitude, skills, learning preference and styles or even the lifestyle of the students to specifically determine what method or strategy is to be employed fitted for the complex world of generation z. And most of this strategy goes back to how this generation were named: the digital natives, the digital generation.

Generation z live in an open, easy and digital book environment where information is just few clicks away, one article is just one scroll of a mouse, countries and culture can be learned through one swipe, communication is as short as a text or a tweet, and where learning could take place on a three minute video.

This big leap from traditional learning to digital learning forces every school to flip and design their curriculums implicitly to accommodate the needs of the students. Online learning and flexible delivery of the content became the salient features of this curriculum where learning takes place outside the classroom and

teachers became an expert facilitator of engaging and practicing the learned, acquired and required skill for the outside world.

Unable to adapt to this existing learning system of generation z would result to failure. Contrary to what many believe, learner's today are not failing the existing educational system, it's actually the other way around: **Our system is killing the process of student's learning. We failed to communicate the information, we blindly refuse to use the needed tools to deliver the information, and we don't speak in ways the student can understand the information.**

It is then a must that every educator must have a thorough understanding on how to properly deliver these information. Raising generational awareness, understanding what is shaping primary and secondary students and identifying collective traits may aide teachers bridge the generation gap and reach their students more effectively. And one way to be able to do that is to determine their learning characteristics and preferences which would allow each teacher to diagnose the proper strategy and techniques to be employed for such communication demands. This generation doesn't expect us to know all about their lifestyle, nor do they want us to embrace their culture. They are simply seeking understanding and respect.(McCrindle, Mark, 2016)

This challenge may pose a question on limited resources that schools may have which restrain most teachers to adapt the modern teacher scheme but we are never called as teacher for that, aye? Like Mark McCrindle always says "Schools are 19th Century institutions using 20th Century buildings to teach 21st Century students and we wonder why traditional education sometimes struggle to connect. So if they don't learn the way we teach, then let's teach the way we learn."

Hence this study.

BODY:

Generation z were born in an environment where structured classrooms became flexible and online, where electronic document is as accurate as the printed page, where tablets replaced the books in the library, where videos served as tutors, and where universal icons and images replaced words for communication. They were different from the well-studied millenials, they represent a new era of generation where learning styles and preference is unique and therefore must be understand thoroughly.

Generation Z Learning Characteristics and Preference

1. Generation Z needs access to technology when learning.

Technology is extremely important to the members of Generation Z. The true digital natives consumed by technology, they have never known life without personal computers, mobile phones, gaming systems, MP3

players and the Internet. (Mat Salleh, Mahbob, & Baharudin, 2017)& (Pratel, 2017) Technology is embedded seamlessly in Gen Zs' lives to the point that taking away these technology would mean removing what is being part of their life. A full 40% of Gen Z are self-identified digital device addicts. (Beall, 2017)

Hence, access to technological tools and allowing them to use it in taking advantage of their drive is a need for every generation z's classroom. Instead of taking devices away in the classroom, incorporate them into activities that promote searching for credible information. (Wondergem, 2017) It's anticipated that computerized methods of learning will continue to expand, and members of generation Z prefer this type of learning. (Pratel, 2017)

Generation z enjoy the use of fast-paced online multimedia for entertainment, play and interaction. (Breibur, 2017) Beginning in the early childhood, if they do not know the answer to a question, they were thought to "Google it" or even better, "ask Siri". (Elmore, 2017) One way to adapt to this learning preference is to incorporate online learning as much as possible. Multiple sources of information like learning management systems for assignments, video lectures and tutorials, self-learning mode and interactive forums is found to retain more information to this new tech – driven generation.(Pratel, 2017)

Yet, connectivity has also lowered Zs age of innocence and confronted them with realities that used to belong to the adult world. It has also made them the target of unprecedented online marketing campaigns and cyber bullying. These negative aspects have to be carefully monitored in class. Watch out for abusive vocabulary or gestures, use sites that provide filters or let you monitor students' conversations and always encourage positive feedback and praise. (Breibur, 2017)

Mediating teaching with a technological device, even in the simplest way — such as asking students to use their mobiles for recording themselves or their peers for dictation or taking a picture for a description—will work wonders, leading them to connect more smoothly with learning objectives, and foster and strengthen friendship bonds and citizenship across geographic or temporal boundaries. (Breibur, 2017)

2. Generation Z preferred learning content divided into small chunks.

Generation Z has 8 second attention span. In the classroom, the average student's attention span is seven to ten minutes; but online, it is at 8 seconds. (Rothman) A short attention span requires information to be delivered in rapid, short bursts if it is to be understood. (Harmanto) Thus, dividing time with students into smaller bites and segments of content to enable them to stay engaged more hours in the long run (Elmore, 2017) is proven to be an effective approach to this generation.

Continued interactions with a fast-paced, sensory laden, multimedia environment predispose/influence a brain to a shorter attention span. That has a lot to do with hypertext, which encourages learners to point or click on a link to get the information they need without reading all of the text. “Keyword spotting” is a preferred strategy to locate needed information. Access to too much data makes Gen Z go for the quick answer rather than the longer problem-solving approach. They may be hard to teach, easily bored and ready to move into the next thing. Due to this, learning needs to be delivered in smaller “bites.” (Rothman)

Additionally, although Z’s are profiled as hyper connected, they find it difficult to associate data. Clicking on hyperlinks has facilitated their access to information but weakened the ability to establish relationships about facts, objects or files. It has also affected the way in which they utilize information since they gather, store and analyse it in a horizontal, equal-value mode. (Breibur, 2017)

Having long periods of lecture or expecting students to focus on the same topic for an extended length of time will not hold the attention of Generation Z students. Students need for short bursts of communication, faculty should talk briefly about content and then allow students to apply the information and test their knowledge. (Hampton & Keys, 2017)

In general, Generation Z prefers micro learning; with so much information trying to get past their filter, standing out from the noise is key to engagement. Keeping it simple, but sparking their curiosity can hook them into paying attention to your mission. (Wong, 2017)

3. Generation Z wants immediacy during learning

Because Gen Zers have an overreliance on technology for answers to their questions and for maintaining social connections, they have no time for delays. (Wong, 2017) The acceleration of the digital world has reduced their attention span, provided instant gratification, and placed information a few clicks away from them. (Breibur, 2017)

Technology aided instruction should work seamlessly. They demand immediacy- access to social connections, feedback and content must be available right away in order to pass through that 8 second filter and capture their focus. (Wong, 2017) Gaming experiences have provided them immediate but changing rewards after meeting expectations and demands. (Cook, n.d.) Exposure to the internet had made Generation Z impatient and require instant gratification, introvert and disengaged with the society. (Mat Salleh, Mahbob, & Baharudin, 2017) It is believed that our constant bombardment of small bits of information from Twitter, Facebook or TV with its six second patterns of imaging is rewiring the brain to expect information to be delivered in short, rapid bursts. (Rothman)

The most pressing need is for immediate response - whether it is feedback in a class, answer to a question, or their most recent tweet. (Cook, n.d.) This new generation values a faster pace of classroom, practice, rehearsal and career advancement that provides frequent feedback for meeting certain benchmarks. (Elmore, 2017)

Prefer random access, graphics first, connected activities, they have a need for speed and instant gratification. Hence, cheating and hacking are considered brilliant in Gen Z's world, but not so in the education world. Instructors don't reward short cuts. (Rothman) This 'Google' generation who take for granted that the information is always readily for them; instant, immediate and free. Such upbringing has made them to be impatient, rebellious and expecting instant result (Turner, 2015).

But we can prepare them for this lifestyle by offering frequent rewards or benefits to incentivize them to stay and keep working. Sometimes the rewards can be easy, yet very meaningful to them—like points for finishing a project on time; affirmation for reaching a goal; or small gifts for hitting a deadline.(Elmore, 2017)

4. Generation Z are born to be multi-tasker.

Generation Z is so comfortable with technology, it stands to reason they are also born multitaskers. They can text, read, watch, talk and eat all at the same time, a talent that stuns adults. (Harmanto) Generation Z can quickly and efficiently shift between work and play, with multiple distractions going on in the background, working on multiple tasks at once. (Beall, 2017) However, while they are able to complete many tasks at once, there is a price to pay.

A neuropsychiatric at Harvard Medical School calls this trend "Acquired Attention Deficit Disorder (AADD)" to describe changes to the inability to focus and analyse more lengthy complex information or issues. (Rothman) & (Harmanto) Hence, it was concluded that this generation does not have capacity to focus and analyse difficult problems, and not being able to work with long term goals (Chun et al., 2015).

Their multi-tasking skill may have pose some big problems on focusing learning content, but this also means that when processing information, generation z do it in the fastest way. The media-rich environment that the Net Generation has become accustomed to appears to have shortened their attention span. If you ask them to work on the same thing for hours, it would probably overwhelm or frustrate them. They will probably enjoy the activities more if they can get several things done simultaneously, because they can usually shift attention rapidly from one task to another. They are generally able to multi-task better than their parents and can split their attention between different activities. Thus, an instructor should not be surprised by seeing a student listening to music, surfing the Internet, and talking to friends on the phone while doing homework.

These diverse activities are all part of the Net Generations' daily lives. (Harmanto) Generation Z students may not pay as much attention to detail as they should, faculty need to spend a lot of time helping students learn how to critically think, to filter data, and to use resulting information to make the best decisions for their patients. (Hampton & Keys, 2017)

5. Generation Z are visual learners.

Some research has shown that the brains of Generation Z are structurally different than those of earlier generations. This has nothing to do with genetics: Generation Z has grown up with tremendous amounts of visually oriented technology (Wooldridge, 2018) so their brains have become wired to sophisticated, complex visual imagery where the use of images, icons and visuals is preferred. As a result, the part of the brain responsible for visual ability is far more developed, making visual forms of learning more effective. (Rothman)

Generation Z craves regular and technology-enhanced learning opportunities. Educational opportunities that are image-based and visually stimulating capture their attention. (Wooldridge, 2018) Interactive games, collaborative projects, advance organizers, challenges, and anything that they can try and see are appreciated. (Rothman)

Gen Z members love to communicate via memes and emojis. Large blocks of text and lengthy readings will likely lose their attention, so try using charts, graphics, different texts, and even different types of media. (Wotapka, 2017) Due to the prevalence of technology in their lives as they developed, the Net Generation feels comfortable in the media-rich environment, surrounded by different kinds of digital devices such as computers, LCD projectors, PDAs, iPods, MP4 and iPhones. Living in this multimedia environment, the Net generations exposes themselves to the interactive computer games and movies, whether they are at home or at school. TV and computers provide rich visual effects which have resulted in them becoming more accustomed to receiving input in this mode. When the Net Generation looks for information online, not only will they try different search engines (like Google and Yahoo), but they also search for interactive materials from YouTube.com. (Harmanto)

6. Generation Z needs social interaction and engagement.

Whether they realize it or not, Gen-Zers are using their social connections as learning tools. This generation is accustomed to intense relationships that aren't limited to a classroom. (Harmanto) Social networking sites and instant messaging were common as Generation Z grew up, so they have little concern for privacy and no problem sharing even the most intimate details of their lives with virtual strangers. (Mat Salleh, Mahbob, & Baharudin, 2017) Thus, creativity and collaboration are natural to them, whether it is a spontaneous or structured activity. (Rothman)

Hence, Generation Z needs social stimulation when learning. Today's youth needs to learn the importance of a face-to-face interaction, especially with the rampant and constant use of technology. Providing opportunities to socialize at school is a great first step for educators. (Pratel, 2017) Reconfiguring the desks in small groups, rather than the traditional desk facing forward, will encourage peer interaction. (Pratel, 2017)

They also like to explore the Internet to learn something new, to make new friends, to make your own photo album, or to learn a new tool for blogging and more. (Mat Salleh, Mahbob, & Baharudin, 2017) They are curating videos or creating videos as artists who want to express themselves. (Elmore, 2017) By building a social community beyond the walls of the classroom and making ourselves available through social apps, some learner may feel comfortable asking questions. They are also used to freely expressing their opinions online, so make sure you encourage collaboration between them through forums, group discussions, and mentoring. (Wooldridge, 2018)

The Net Generation enjoys working on teams with peers, using collaborative tools like Google Apps. In general, these students are more likely to prefer learning in a supportive environment with teamwork, where slower learners are supported by the fast learners. An activity, such as a Wiki project that can be undertaken with their instructors and peers is probably preferred by the Net Generation more than an individual assignment. (Harmanto)

Although Generation Z students enjoy working in groups and in social settings, they want learning in a group to be an option and do not want to be mandated to participate in a group. (Hampton & Keys, 2017) Generation Z is explained as individualistic, self-absorbed and less team oriented than the previous generation (Turner, 2015). They are a generation that has the ability to form huge communities and a constant communication loop with people they have never met, and never will meet on the net; paradoxically this generation is collaborative, chatty and sociable on the net, yet in 'the real world' they tend to be less well able to develop personal relationships. (Mat Salleh, Mahbob, & Baharudin, 2017) While Gen Z learners will likely need less training on technology, they may require considerable support in their development of offline interpersonal communication.

The old saying in education circles still rings true for today's students: 'they don't care how much you know until they know how much you care!' Communicating to this generation requires more than just good content and new technology – it needs engagement and involvement. The more we create an environment conducive to engaging with the head (knowledge), hands (application) and heart (inspiration), the more likely they learning will be embedded, opportunities enlarged and futures shaped. (McCrinkle, Mark, 2016)

7. Generation Z are globally connected.

Millennials were considered the first “global” generation with the development of the internet, but as more of the world comes online — Generation Z will become more global in their thinking, interactions, and relatability. (Beall, 2017) Evidence shows that Generation Z’s are more socially responsible, health conscious, and environmentally aware (Breibur, 2017) and globalization appears in their culture or even in their language, (Barreiro & Bozutti, 2017) and by getting them to contribute to the global community responsibly leaving impact or positive mark, they may feel motivated to realigned information towards deeper learning. (Breibur, 2017)

The impact of digital technologies has made Gen Z a global generation with a local mind-set. They share preferences with peers from the most diverse parts of the world, but without losing interests in local affairs. It has also democratized power relations and redefined teacher-student relationships through equal access to information. They have a very personal voice that is valued and considered online (Breibur, 2017) Yet Zs may know more about ongoing issues on the other side of the globe than what is going on next door. Childhood has been more of an indoor experience for them and has therefore characterized this special way of connecting with others and reality. (Breibur, 2017) Diversity will be an expectation of Generation Z. (Beall, 2017)

8. Generation Z demands relevance of learning content.

Generation Z needs learning content that has relevance on a global scale. These learners are practical, savvy, and thrive on a good challenge, especially when it reflects their personal interests and is accompanied by instant gratification. (Wondergem, 2017) Generation Z grew up with even busier schedules than Millennials did, so they like to maximize what little spare time they have. Immediacy have always been at their fingertips, so in any lesson that they have, they’re going to demand relevance first.” (Wotapka, 2017) There is no point in going to a friend’s movie night with a rented DVD if they only have a streaming service. Similarly, we must communicate in the most appropriate format for those we are reaching. So in understanding the communication styles of our students we will be better equipped to reach them. (McCrindle, Mark, 2016)

Today's job market is more concerned with skills than education. Employers want to know that a candidate has the skills to complete the job. It's important that teachers recognize this trend and teach in a style that focuses on competency with job-related skills rather than a focus on a specific academic discipline (Pratel, 2017) though some educators find some difficulty linking theory with practice. (Barreiro & Bozutti, 2017) You'll also want to coach your students to actively think about these skills and what they enjoy. Before choosing a vocation or degree, you'll want your students to have a clear idea of their long-term goals and make decisions based on this preface. (Pratel, 2017)

9. Generation Z lives with a very strong parental impact.

Generation Zs' parents are generally Gen Xers who have brought them up focusing on safety and individualism and have encouraged them to be realistic, innovative in education, and to find their own way. (Breibur, 2017) Some Zs may come from smaller families with traditional values, or they may live in larger, extended, or blended multi-generational households with their elder siblings also dwelling at home and in close contact with retired grandparents or step family members. These modern family models, displaying blurred gender-roles and alternative lifestyles, have contributed to shape Zs' mindsets towards, acceptance of diversity and inclusivity. (Breibur, 2017)

However, Gen X parents tend to have a helicopter parenting style, which results to premature maturity of Gen-Z's. (Breibur, 2017) The curling generation' due to their parents diligently sweeping away the obstacle that lies in their path, they march effortlessly towards their future. On the other meaning, they are being spoon-fed by their parents. In this case, there are tendencies that they would demand the same atmosphere to be created at schools. (Mat Salleh, Mahbob, & Baharudin, 2017)

Gen Z students do not fall for superheroes or impossible missions. The recently released Global Young People Report (2017) revealed that 89% of the adolescents surveyed indicated that their parents were the most significant influencing factor on their values. Fostering strong home-school partnerships will therefore enhance Zs' learning experience and channel parental interest in a profitable way. (Breibur, 2017)

Lastly, be real with Generation Z. Students expect to obtain value from the educational experience and be prepared to move into a career that offers job security. They want to continually learn/ develop and expect to be mentored by faculty and others. Thus, educators need to ensure that students understand the value of course content, practicum experiences, and how this information will be essential for career success. (Hampton & Keys, 2017)

10. Generation Z are highly entrepreneurial

According to Gen Z marketing strategist Deep Patel, "the newly developing high tech and highly networked world has resulted in an entire generation thinking and acting more entrepreneurially." Generation Z desires more independent work environments. As a matter of fact, 72% of teens say they want to start a business someday. (Beall, 2017) This identifying factors can be traced back to the recession in 2008, from their frugality, to their value of experiences, and increased likelihood to become entrepreneurs. (Beall, 2017) This can be further verified on the survey conducted by North Western University in which almost two thirds of the students wanted

to learn about entrepreneurship, including how to start their own business and forty-two percent wanted to be self-employed. (Hampton & Keys, 2017)

The Challenge to Educators of Today

This generation grew up with technology, and for them, it's probably hard to go without their devices. (Beall, 2017)

And with this devices that provides convenient access to the outside world via social media, wide array of information can be obtained effortlessly, but not the knowledge, literacy and maturity to verify the authenticity of the information. In which in this case, one thing that had gone missing is the ability of critical thinking. Without critical thinking, they will not be able to filter the information thus will only underline what bests according to their needs and desire. In many cases, such situation will most likely result to emergence of negative behavior such as vandalism (Mat Salleh, Mahbob, & Baharudin, 2017)

Research by Jaleniauskiene & Juceviciene, (2015) indicated that due to intensively expose to the internet; they prefer watching video instead of reading hardcopy media; books and manuals. If earlier method of using paperback were used in delivering a lesson or a message such as newspaper, textbook and manuals, Generation Z would prefer getting it from a website that is much more interesting and alive, which is hypertext. Despite of being highly tech savvy and extensively attached to the technology for navigating and using information to develop their skills, unfortunately according to Cowan, (2014), their factual knowledge level base remains immature and very least on information literacy. (Mat Salleh, Mahbob, & Baharudin, 2017)

The classroom challenge is that learners are now digital and many instructors (digital immigrants) are still analog; i.e., they teach and put knowledge into students' heads instead of being a facilitator of learning. Instructors are at a disadvantage because they aren't as comfortable with technology as their learners, and yet they must be prepared to teach the "content of the future" using software, hardware, digital, technological, and social media. There is a need to provide meaningful, tech-focused, professional development for instructors as they transition from a traditional learning model to one that is transformational. (Rothman)

Educating our youth has never before been so challenging and fascinating. Schools are called to prepare Gen Z students for adult life by teaching them the 'dispositions' (Claxton, 2013) they will need to succeed in life, in the future. And educators and parents are urged to empower them effectively to face uncertainty and change.

CONCLUSION:

A journey of a thousand miles begins with a simple generationally-oriented step: understanding the unique characteristics to maximize potential that is hope to leverage positive outcomes. (Hampton & Keys, 2017)

This systematic review have revealed the learning characteristics and preference of the Generation Z which could be used by educators, in general, to their learners. These could be summarized as follows:

- 1. Generation Z needs access to technology when learning.**
- 2. Generation Z preferred learning content divided into small chunks.**
- 3. Generation Z wants immediacy during learning**
- 4. Generation Z are born to be multi-tasker.**
- 5. Generation Z are visual learners.**
- 6. Generation Z needs social interaction and engagement.**
- 7. Generation Z are globally connected.**
- 8. Generation Z demands relevance of learning content.**
- 9. Generation Z lives with a very strong parental impact.**
- 10. Generation Z are highly entrepreneurial**

Issues may arise regarding the emergence of negative behaviour due to the constant use of technology, inability to develop critical thinking, and teacher's preparation for the digital integration.

The bottom line is that a traditional educational practices require thoughtful change in order to meet the needs of this generation. Gen Z wants to be part of the process of learning, not passive bystanders. They are resourceful learners whose attention span is hindered by a constant bombardment of information. They make up for that with their creativity, self-discovery skills, speed to process information, and the ability to handle multidimensional learning experiences.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Barreiro, S. C., & Bozutti, D. F. (2017). Challenges and Difficulties to Teaching Engineering to Generation Z: A Case Research. *Propositos Y Representaciones*, Volume 5, Number 2, 127 - 183.

Beall, G. (2017, November 6). 8 Key Differences Between Gen Z and Millennials. Retrieved from Huffpost: <file:///C:/Users/Don%20Cadadayon/Downloads/generation%20z/8%20Key%20Differences%20between%20Gen%20Z%20and%20Millennials%20-%20HuffPost.html>

Breiburd, S. A. (2017, September 13). 4 Simple Tactics to Engage Better win Gen Z's Students. Retrieved from Corwin Connect: <file:///C:/Users/Don%20Cadadayon/Downloads/generation%20z/4%20Simple%20Tactics%20to%20Engage%20Better%20With%20Gen%20Z%20Students%20-%20Corwin%20Connect.html>

Cook, V. (n.d.). Engaging Generation Z Students. Retrieved from University of Illinois Springfield COLRS: http://info.shiftelearning.com/blog/millennials-elearning-industry?utm_source=hs_email&utm_medium=email&utm_content=21296196&_hsenc=p2ANqtz-81MNpgmqrNECiOsGR3mQn9oUuGdqeKslYEB5Zc4UnHKL8L_GIaho8vtrDtvXcEMRW9vXMMcMfWVvAF6fsApD1zI9vmA&_hsmi=21296196

Elmore, T. (2017, June 20). Six Simple Ways to Better Engage Generation Z . Retrieved from Growing Leaders: <file:///C:/Users/Don%20Cadadayon/Downloads/generation%20z/6%20Simple%20Engagement%20Strategies%20for%20Teaching%20Gen%20Z%20Students.html>

Hampton, D. C., & Keys, Y. (2017). Generation Z Students: Will They Change Our Nursing Classrooms? *Journal of Nursing Education and Practice*, Volume 7, Number 4, 111 - 115.

Harmanto, B. (n.d.). Teaching English to Generation Z Students (New Concept of Young Learners).

Mat Salleh, M. S., Mahbob, N. N., & Baharudin, N. S. (2017). Overview of "Generation Z" Behavioural Characteristic and Its Effect Towards Hostel Facility. *International Journal of Real State Studies*, Volume 11, Number 2, 59 - 67.

McCrindle, Mark. (2016, April 29). Generation Z at School. Retrieved from mccrindle blog:
file:///C:/Users/Don%20Cadaydayon/Downloads/generation%20z/Generation%20Z%20at%20school.html

Pratel, G. (2017, January 31). 3 Ways to Adapt Your Teaching to Gen Z's Habits. Retrieved from teacherswithapps:
file:///C:/Users/Don%20Cadaydayon/Downloads/generation%20z/3%20Ways%20to%20Adapt%20Your%20Teaching%20to%20Gen%20Z%E2%80%99s%20Habits%20-%20Teachers%20With%20Apps.html

Rothman, D. (n.d.). A Tsunami of Learners Called Generation Z.

Wongergem, K. (2017, September 9). Here Comes Z: Strategies to Engage New Generation of College Students. Retrieved from eLearning Industry, Educational Technology:
file:///C:/Users/Don%20Cadaydayon/Downloads/generation%20z/Here%20Comes%20Z_%20Strategies%20To%20Engage%20A%20New%20Generation%20Of%20College%20Students%20-%20eLearning%20Industry.html

Wooldridge, D. (2018, January 3). 5 Unique Generation Z Characteristics and How to Train them. Retrieved from ttc Innovations:
file:///C:/Users/Don%20Cadaydayon/Downloads/generation%20z/5%20Unique%20Generation%20Z%20Characteristics%20&%20How%20to%20Train%20Them%20-%20ttcInnovations%20_%20ttcInnovations.html

Wotapka, D. (2017, May 9). How to Teach Gen Z Students. Retrieved from AICPA Org:
file:///C:/Users/Don%20Cadaydayon/Downloads/generation%20z/How%20to%20Teach%20Gen%20Z%20Students.html